

Review article

Synthesis and Function of Multi-modality Probe for Early Tumor Diagnosis in Mouse

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ABSTRACT

Multi-modality optical imaging probes make an appearance as precious instrument for improving apprehension susceptibility and correctness, which is critical in malady identification and therapy. We focus on current advancements in the integration of fluorescence imaging especially optical fluorescence imaging probes various fluorescence-imaging modalities, for instance, X-ray computed tomography magnetic resonance imaging positron emission tomography, and single-photon emission computed tomography and photoacoustic imaging (PAI). Imaging methods shortly reviewed highlight the benefits, drawbacks approach, as well as the requirement for more multi-modality optical imaging (MOI) probe formation. It focuses on how current layout techniques used to make multimodality optical fluorescence imaging probes that are physio chemically and biologically well matched, as well as how to overcome the inherent risks of each imaging method using a multimodality technique with advanced detection sensitivity and accuracy. The current evolution of probes that integrate imaging distinction substances is the subject of this article. The goal of multimodality fluorescence probes the better of the inherent limitations of every one imaging modality by combining complimentary data from several modalities to enhance responsiveness and correctness that are critical in disease identification and therapy.

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INTRODUCTION

The requirement for sensitive and accurate imaging methods in medical diagnosis and treatments is the major focus. There have been several important advancements in tomography mechanization in both diagnosing and advanced translational investigation and its applications in recent decade [1].

Optical-imaging, especially fluorescence imaging, extensively employed in histology and gained increasing therapeutic importance as a molecular imaging modality with applications that include molecular responsiveness at the picomolar level, Peptides, proteins, antibody fragments, nanoparticles, phages, and aptamers proteins, antibody fragments [2].

Clinical investigation demonstrate that utilized of optical-imaging to control matter like tissues surgical removal of the organs improves cancer tissue removal and reduces local recurrence Fluorescence imaging is

restricted by deep penetration owing to photon dispersal and light debilitation in biological tissue. Quantitative or tomographic data is likewise difficult to supply. Multichannel imaging is a technique to control the restriction of fluorescence imaging and achieving non-invasive lesions by combining two or more imaging techniques [3]. Because of all modality utilizes separated substances with different chemical combination, magnitude susceptible to solution like characteristics, it is challenging to use several contrasting agents in a single dosage to ensure spatiotemporal consistency across all imaging methods. As a result, for multimodality imaging applications, an isolated probe that incorporates multiple-imaging at variance materials is favored [4]. Furthermore, using a multimodality probe can minimize the amount of time spent on poisonous assessment and the action of drugs on body studies during diagnosis of the disease.

Our goal in this paper is to investigate and arrange a high-level summary of this growing research topic, focusing on the multimodality fluorescence probe design techniques rather than biological applications. To understand the imaging approach necessity for multi-modality optical imaging probes, there is a short presentation to the dominance and limitations of frequently employed imaging modality [5]. Second, strategies implemented to design multimodality optical fluorescence imaging probes that are physic-chemically and biologically compatible for the purpose to control the fundamental restriction of each imaging technique and achieve greater sensitivity and accuracy for early disease diagnosis. Our research focuses on fluorescent imaging (FI) probes that combine fluorescence reporting groups (fluorophores) with other substances utilized in the X-ray computed tomography (CT), single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), and also in photo acoustic imaging (PAI) magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) positron emission tomography (PET) [6]. Extra justification components, including as earmark classification and medicinal drugs, also incorporated in the probes.

Imaging model in combination with other models of imaging has become a viable solution. It is important develop supportive imaging different substances in tandem with improvements in imaging methods. They should improve sensitivity in order to disclose physiological structure and disease-specific molecular information [7]. Modality selection in diagnostic imaging, on the other hand, influenced as seeing, as high-level of responsiveness and high magnification are difficult in amalgamation with modality. Different imaging modalities' complimentary qualities used to produce significant benefits. Computed tomography (CT), Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), PET, SPECT, and photoacoustic imaging are some of the imaging modalities utilized or investigated in clinical to diagnose the disease (PAI) [8].

MRI and CT produce multispectral bodily pictures, although contrast agent sensitivity is relatively poor. High sensitivity, limitless penetration depth, and measurable findings are all benefits of SPECT and PET. These modalities commonly employed to track pharmacokinetics, bio distribution, and accumulation at target sites, although they have low spatial resolution. PAI is a high-resolution imaging technology that is still relatively new. When employed in soft tissues, it gives excellent contrast, although detection is restricted [9].

Optical fluorescence imaging (OFI)

Optical fluorescence imaging utilized fluorescence-microscopy to examine *in-vivo* and *ex-vivo* molecular methods both tissue samples, has grown to be one of the most significant time-lapse photography methods. OFI has recently become more popular in imaging-guided surgery. Quantum dots, lanthanide-doped up conversion nanoparticles, organic dyes, fluorescent proteins, and aggregation induced emission luminogens are among OFI's fluorescence reporting groups [10]. Because of light attenuation and scattering, as well as Autofluorescence from endogenous molecules such as cytochromes causes interference. Hemoglobin, and

water molecules, for in vivo imaging applications, fluorescence emissions in the visible range (400–650 nm) are typically of limited value.

Near-infrared fluorescence (NIRF) imaging

NIRF imaging detects fluorescence emissions in the range of 650 to 900 nm, has a low background tissue autofluorescence for higher diffusion depth, and is better suited for in-vivo presymptomatic and therapeutic imaging research. In multimodality imaging, a variety of NIR dyes are employed. The only NIRF dye authorized for clinical usage in the United States is indocyanine green (ICG) [11]. Furthermore, because of its even greater tissue autofluorescence, better image contrast, and lower photo toxicity and photo bleaching, NIRF photography is another biological window (1000–1400 nm), known as the over-thousand near-infrared (OTN) imaging, has got a lot of focus in applications of in-vivo imaging. Examples of OTN fluorescence imaging agents are Quantum dots, rare-earth doped materials, Ni-doped magnetic nanocrystals, and single-wall carbon nanotubes [12, 13].

Design and study of multimodality probes

A lysine-cleavable protease activatable agent's activation process is depicted in this diagram. The imaging agent is injectable and is a high-molecular-weight molecule (550 kDa), lengthily-circulating with defensive side chains (methoxypoly, ethylene glycol) that is highlighted in clinical studies and consists of a backbone of a poly-L-lysine and defensive side chains (methoxypoly [ethylene glycol]) [14]. Multiple NIR fluorochromes are attached to this backbone. Self-quenching of the imaging agent happens due to their close proximity and fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET). Because there is a low circulating background signal, quenching from an imaging standpoint the imaging agent at baseline is very beneficial.

In atheromata *In-vivo* molecular imaging of proteolytic activity, panels through atomic black-blood MRI of an apoE/thoracic mouse's aorta (arrow, top panel). In vivo fluorescence molecular tomography (FMT, lower panel) of the related anatomic region after injection of the protease-activatable drug displays localized NIRF prompts in the aorta. Sudan IV flat coloring of the aorta revealed a strong association between *ex vivo* fluorescence reflectance imaging and NIR fluorescent plaques. A cysteine protease used to activate the imaging agent, matched highly with the tiny NIRF prompts in atheroma.

Figure 1. Nanoprobe of multilayer modality OFI/CT attached with different target groups

To generate melanin nano-particles with high-tide water monodispersed and uniformity, the granules, it is 1st disintegrate in 0.1 N NaOH aqueous solution and subsequently counteract undergoing sonication. RGD was additionally linked to the MNP for tumor targeting after PEG surface modification [15]. The resultant MNPs then chelated with Fe³⁺ and/or ⁶⁴Cu²⁺ for PAI/MRI/PET multimodal imaging.

Figure 2. Synthesis of one shell probe from multi steps of modality OFC/CT. [16]

The nanoprobe's low toxicity and extended blood circulation duration make it ideal for applications including preoperative inquiry and intraoperative imaging [17]. Created NIR constantly luminous nanoparticle ($Zn_{2.94}Ga_{1.96}Ge_2O_{10}:Cr^{3+}, Pr^{3+}$, abbreviated as ZGGO: Cr, Pr) in this case. It selected as a central to build the nanoparticles and also to core shell nanoparticle was also created by the TaOx shell that is functioned as CT contrast agent after being excited in vitro at 254 nm and then injected into a living animal for in vivo imaging with NIR emission at 695 nm [18]. The reagent 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane used to cover the superficial TaOx surface with a coating of improved silica. The surface of the produced nano-particles featured amine groups for easier combine with PEG series also contain cyclic CNGRCGG peptides as the targeting group [19]. NIRF or CT imaging, the developed small nano-probes, NGR-PEG-ZGGO:Cr,Pr@TaOx@SiO₂, could identify tumour location in HepG2 tumor-bearing nude mice in vivo [16].

Figure3. Imaging probe of an activated multi-modality OFI/MRI imaging probe

Clinicians frequently employ inert gado-linium (III) ion network including diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid or 1, 4, 7, 10-tetraazacyclododecane-N, N', N'', N'''-tetra acetic acid. Multi-modality OFI/MRI imaging probes formed directly combining an organic fluorophore to a Gd(III) chelator [20]. Ratio of 1:1 mol of MRI and optical constituents, on the other hand, produced in a sensitivity mismatch between the two imaging modalities [21]. The NIR-fluorophore attachment results come out, in increased the cell absorption via organic-anion transporting polypeptides, which is beneficial for cell MRI imaging. The probe assembles in the tumours identified by the OFI; imply that local concentration of MRI contrast agents has to improve further. Gadolinium (III)-Also, use fluorescent dye complexes as ion exchange reaction-activatable or triggered MRI and OFI probes for ion identification. The fluorescent dye undergoes a transition from combination with Gd(III) to free energy state or entangled with metal cation, resulting in a shift in fluorescence [22].

Figure 4. Representation of multi-modality OFI/PET probes design with the radiometal ions.

Ion exchange process used to activate gadolinium (III) autofluorescence radiation phosphorescence dye network as MRI and for ion identification. The fluorescent dye undergoes a transition from association with Gd(III) to untied condition or complexities with metal cation throughout this process, resulting in a shift in fluorescence [23, 24]. Asterisks indicate regions that are mainly Hb-rich, which are produced as a result of blood percolate permeate filter sink in into the tumor concentration via perforated arteries [25]. The chromophore concentrations in arbitrary units shown by color scales.

An extensive transmission solo wall of the carbon nanotube derived NIRF/PAI substances for multi-photodynamic treatment (PDT) and photothermal therapy (PTT) narrate the (PTT) [26]. SWCNT was the firestone non-strongly associated coupled with a molecule called Evans's blue (EB) molecules on its outer side as a position for subsequent to cause to be function to create the multiple functional probes. After that, serum albumin was added to the EB-binding sites to facilitate the extension of chlorin e6, a commonly worn photosensitizer for PDT that serves fluorescence reporting class [27]. Serum albumin used to target the albumin receptor gp60 and SPARC on the surface of cancer cells. In the course of PDT/PTT imaging-guided tumor wastage treatment, this SWCNT-based probe was shown to have enhanced effectiveness [28].

On coronal and sagittal perspectives, SPECT/CT imaging of pulmonary malignancies, no visible tumors (L: lung; H: heart), Fluorescence imaging revealed exterior cancers, Fluorescence imaging of resected lungs revealed many tumors abrasion. A part of the PEG400 chains used may be fixed to the surface of the MBP nanosheets, giving them exceptional colloidal stability and biocompatibility [29]. The injected Bi ions were linked with redundant S atoms, resulting in no harmful H₂S gas being generated during the solvothermal process [30]. More crucially, the Bi integration gives capability and a radiation enhancement effect during RT, whilst the MoS₂ framework gives the MBP nanosheets an outstanding capability [31]. As a result, such an MBP composite nanosystem should be able to perform CT and PA imaging guided combination tumors sensitized RT in vitro and in vivo. To our knowledge, there has not been a single-step, "bottom-up" solvothermal technique for producing 2D MBP composites documented until now. Other 2D MoS₂-based composites might be synthesized using this basic approach [32]. MoS₂/CuSxPEG (MCP), MoS₂/PdSxPEG (MPP), and MoS₂/ZrSxPEG (MZP) nanosheets may be effectively generated [33]. This simple one pot hybridizing approach

will make it easier to mass-produce 2D MoS₂ nanosheets have many functions that are including biomedicine, energy conversion materials and also catalysts.

After the transient stage alteration process, DOX and MoS₂ may enclosed within produced solidified materials, resulting in a 2D MoS₂-based composite PMD implant into the tumor [34]. To our understanding, this is the first semantic development on state changing organic-inorganic composite oleosol to targeted tumor combining treatment combining 2D-inorganic MoS₂ nanosheets with organic PLGA [35]. Dissimilar standard drugs “dispersed in allows combination in vivo tumor photothermal and chemotherapeutic suspension” methods, such a novel localized therapeutic implant comes with a number of benefits A fast-forming PMD implant with a low PTA and medication dose (DOX: 30 g; MoS₂: 75 g). Because the MoS₂ nano-sheets and DOX are packed in a PLGA matrix, they not go to the blood, providing high in vivo biosecurity [36]. Nanosheets MoS₂ with a high NIR light absorption function as big production against substances for photo-acoustic (PA) imaging, allowing PA to monitor the precise position of solid PMD implants. Heat generated by NIR radiation is unable to implant matrix, resulting in control drug free and improved treatment that is used to control the cancer cells outcomes [37].

Because multimodality nanoprobe may give complimentary information from their multi-functional pictures, they are very attractive in order within the living organisms imaging at entire anatomy leve Fe₃O₄ MNPs, NIR-FL QDs and VIS-FL QDs, utilized to create multimodality nanoprobe) [38]. A three-step preparation approach used to synthesize the MQQ-probe. In the first stage, non-ionic surfactant-stabilized without thermodynamically stable isotropic liquid mixtures of oil is used to coat Fe₃O₄ MNPs with silica, as illustrated in Fe₃O₄ MNPs are coated with silica [39]. In a nutshell, the change micelle is made with Tegretol (NP-9) as a nonionic surfactant and cyclohexane as a fluids like solvent [40]. A type of micelle reverse microemulsion with an isotropic and thermodynamically stable phase formed by adding a base catalyst (ammonia). Then, using TEOS as a silica precursor, the silica matrix develops around the Fe₃O₄ NPs. It produces excellent monodisperse silica beads with Fe₃O₄ MNPs in the center after developing the silica matrix for 24 hours [41]. Following that, CdSeTe/CdS QDs and TEOS introduced to the liquid solution in the second stage. Because the original hydrophobic ligands of QDs replaced with hydrolyzed TEOS and surfactant molecules. The hydrophobic QDs bond to the micelle's interfacial layer, allowing them to be incorporated into the reverse microemulsion system [42]. As a result, under micelle formation, silica growth with hydrophobic QDs can proceed easily. A thin shell of QDs/silica forms around the beads after another 24 hours of growth [43]. With the inclusion of CdSe/ZnS QDs and TEOS, the development of the silica matrix in the microemulsion regulated identical method. Fe₃O₄ MNPs, NIR- QDs, and VIS-FL QDs are all encapsulated in a silicon dioxide nano-bead, as predicted [44].

Permit inflammation and discharge of light to flow effective, the matrix should be optically transparent. Silica and calcium phosphate nanoparticles are the most common inorganic matrix used for color encapsulation (CPNPs). Because of its hydrophilic nature, silicic oxide matrix is appealing within a living organisms imaging as it can decrease broad binding and accumulation. It is synthetically unmoving, pellucid and uncomplicated. For years, natural nanocarriers including micelles, and dendrimers, liposomes, utilized for the delivery of drug. Natural organization systems encapsulating NIRF dyes for cancer molecular imaging described, such as the utilization of resolvable microporous nanoparticles as NIRF dye carriers for tumor imaging. NIRF dye consist of nanoparticles, SWNTs, quantum dots (QDs), and metal nanoclusters are among [45,46] the well-known DCN NIRF nanoprobe [47].

Figure 5. Representation of nanoprobe in living organisms on nanomaterials NIRF

CONCLUSION

Fluorescence imaging which amalgamates with multimodality imaging and other sense modality come out as a strong technique to increasing responsiveness and correctness, both of which are crucial for better disease diagnosis and therapy. Imaging techniques, equipment, and artificial procedure advancements carry on with drive multimodality imaging approaches and probe development to new heights. Although optical imaging coupled with novel, imaging modalities is intriguing, growing and unmet clinical requirements, such as image-guided surgery, cancer, and personalized medicine, will ultimately drive future multimodality probe development. The FDA has not yet authorized any imaging probes for clinical utilized in double modality imaging. The majority of today's probes created and tested for use in preclinical biomedical research, when data from the two of them intense tissue materials and surface immunological imaging was mandatory validate against everyone.

Each unique union of many fluorescence-imaging probes explored in terms of its potential. The difficulties in designing a multimodality optical fluorescence probe are enormous. The substances qualities of difference medium and the bioactivity of the matter are important, the identity of the probe's establishment is also important. When targeted lot, enables the healing roles are incorporated, the complexity increases. Selecting the optimum mixtures of materials and contrast agents, figuring out how to put them together, and achieving optimal characteristics outline great pick outadd to are not straightforward tasks. The procedure will need systems engineering as well as several rounds of painstaking tuning. All of these initiatives might promote to

the development of new therapeutic medium to diagnose and disease, as well as effective interventions to help patients live prolonged and better existence.

Disclaimer

The article has not been previously presented or published, and is not part of a thesis project.

Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

REFERENCES

1. Alberti CJRMPS. From molecular imaging in preclinical/clinical oncology to theranostic applications in targeted tumor therapy. 2012;16(14):1925-33.
2. Chang K, Jaffer FJJoNC. Advances in fluorescence imaging of the cardiovascular system. 2008;15(3):417-28.
3. Louie AJCr. Multimodality imaging probes: design and challenges. 2010;110(5):3146-95.
4. Taggart DP, Choudhary B, Anastasiadis K, Abu-Omar Y, Balacumaraswami L, Pigott DW. Preliminary experience with a novel intraoperative fluorescence imaging technique to evaluate the patency of bypass grafts in total arterial revascularization. The Annals of thoracic surgery. 2003;75(3):870-3.
5. Weissleder R, Mahmood U. Molecular imaging. Radiology. 2001;219(2):316-33.
6. Tung C-H, Bremer C, Weissleder R. In vivo Imaging of Protease Activity and Drug Screening. Peptides: The Wave of the Future: Springer; 2001. p. 986-7.
7. Kelly K, Alencar H, Funovics M, Mahmood U, Weissleder R. Detection of invasive colon cancer using a novel, targeted, library-derived fluorescent peptide. Cancer research. 2004;64(17):6247-51.
8. Sun Y, Ding M, Zeng X, Xiao Y, Wu H, Zhou H, et al. Novel bright-emission small-molecule NIR-II fluorophores for in vivo tumor imaging and image-guided surgery. Chemical science. 2017;8(5):3489-93.
9. He S, Song J, Qu J, Cheng ZJCSR. Crucial breakthrough of second near-infrared biological window fluorophores: design and synthesis toward multimodal imaging and theranostics. 2018;47(12):4258-78.
10. Zhao J, Chen J, Ma S, Liu Q, Huang L, Chen X, et al. Recent developments in multimodality fluorescence imaging probes. 2018;8(3):320-38.
11. Namikawa T, Sato T, Hanazaki KJSt. Recent advances in near-infrared fluorescence-guided imaging surgery using indocyanine green. 2015;45(12):1467-74.
12. Kamimura M, Saito R, Hyodo H, Tsuji K, Umeda IO, Fujii H, et al. Over-1000 nm near-infrared fluorescence and SPECT/CT dual-modal in vivo imaging based on rare-earth doped ceramic nanophosphors. 2016;29(4):525-32.
13. Qin M-Y, Yang X-Q, Wang K, Zhang X-S, Song J-T, Yao M-H, et al. In vivo cancer targeting and fluorescence-CT dual-mode imaging with nanoprobe based on silver sulfide quantum dots and iodinated oil. 2015;7(46):19484-92.
14. Wouters FS, Verveer PJ, Bastiaens PI. Imaging biochemistry inside cells. Trends in cell biology. 2001;11(5):203-11.
15. Soltesz EG, Laurence RG, Alec M, Cohn LH, Mihaljevic T, Frangioni JV, editors. Image-guided quantification of cardioplegia delivery during cardiac surgery. The heart surgery forum; 2007: NIH Public Access.
16. Lu Y-C, Yang C-X, Yan X-PJN. Radiopaque tantalum oxide coated persistent luminescent nanoparticles as multimodal probes for in vivo near-infrared luminescence and computed tomography bioimaging. 2015;7(42):17929-37.
17. Zhu B, Jaffer FA, Ntziachristos V, Weissleder R. Development of a near infrared fluorescence catheter: operating characteristics and feasibility for atherosclerotic plaque detection. Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics. 2005;38(15):2701.
18. Becker V, Vercauteren T, von Weyhern CH, Prinz C, Schmid RM, Meining A. High-resolution miniprobe-based confocal microscopy in combination with video mosaicing (with video). Gastrointestinal endoscopy. 2007;66(5):1001-7.
19. Nahrendorf M, Sosnovik DE, Waterman P, Swirski FK, Pande AN, Aikawa E, et al. Dual channel optical tomographic imaging of leukocyte recruitment and protease activity in the healing myocardial infarct. Circulation research. 2007;100(8):1218-25.

20. Guo K, Berezin MY, Zheng J, Akers W, Lin F, Teng B, et al. Near infrared-fluorescent and magnetic resonance imaging molecular probe with high T 1 relaxivity for in vivo multimodal imaging. 2010;46(21):3705-7.
21. Dumont E, Reutelingsperger C, Smits J, Daemen M, Doevendans P, Wellens H, et al. Real-time imaging of apoptotic cell-membrane changes at the single-cell level in the beating murine heart. *Nature medicine*. 2001;7(12):1352.
22. Dong D, Jing X, Zhang X, Hu X, Wu Y, Duan CJT. Gadolinium (III)-fluorescein complex as a dual modal probe for MRI and fluorescence zinc sensing. 2012;68(1):306-10.
23. Ghosh SC, Ghosh P, Wilganowski N, Robinson H, Hall MA, Dickinson G, et al. Multimodal chelation platform for near-infrared fluorescence/nuclear imaging. 2013;56(2):406-16.
24. Peng D, Du Y, Shi Y, Mao D, Jia X, Li H, et al. Precise diagnosis in different scenarios using photoacoustic and fluorescence imaging with dual-modality nanoparticles. *Nanoscale*. 2016;8(30):14480-8.
25. Duan S, Yang Y, Zhang C, Zhao N, Xu FJ. NIR-Responsive Polycationic Gatekeeper-Cloaked Hetero-Nanoparticles for Multimodal Imaging-Guided Triple-Combination Therapy of Cancer. *Small*. 2017;13(9):1603133.
26. Xie L, Wang G, Zhou H, Zhang F, Guo Z, Liu C, et al. Functional long circulating single walled carbon nanotubes for fluorescent/photoacoustic imaging-guided enhanced phototherapy. *Biomaterials*. 2016;103:219-28.
27. Tang L, Zhang F, Yu F, Sun W, Song M, Chen X, et al. Croconaine nanoparticles with enhanced tumor accumulation for multimodality cancer theranostics. *Biomaterials*. 2017;129:28-36.
28. Lütje S, Rijpkema M, Franssen GM, Fracasso G, Helfrich W, Eek A, et al. Dual-modality image-guided surgery of prostate cancer with a radiolabeled fluorescent anti-PSMA monoclonal antibody. *Journal of Nuclear Medicine*. 2014;55(6):995-1001.
29. Liu T, Wang C, Cui W, Gong H, Liang C, Shi X, et al. Combined photothermal and photodynamic therapy delivered by PEGylated MoS₂ nanosheets. *Nanoscale*. 2014;6(19):11219-25.
30. Wang S, Li K, Chen Y, Chen H, Ma M, Feng J, et al. Biocompatible PE Gylated MoS₂ nanosheets: Controllable bottom-up synthesis and highly efficient photothermal regression of tumor. *Biomaterials*. 2015;39:206-17.
31. Zafiropoulou I, Katsiotis M, Boukos N, Karakassides M, Stephen S, Tzitzios V, et al. In situ deposition and characterization of MoS₂ nanolayers on carbon nanofibers and nanotubes. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 2013;117(19):10135-42.
32. Xiang Q, Yu J, Jaroniec M. Synergetic effect of MoS₂ and graphene as cocatalysts for enhanced photocatalytic H₂ production activity of TiO₂ nanoparticles. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2012;134(15):6575-8.
33. Zhou W, Yin Z, Du Y, Huang X, Zeng Z, Fan Z, et al. Synthesis of few-layer MoS₂ nanosheet-coated TiO₂ nanobelt heterostructures for enhanced photocatalytic activities. *small*. 2013;9(1):140-7.
34. Liu T, Wang C, Gu X, Gong H, Cheng L, Shi X, et al. Drug delivery with PEGylated MoS₂ nano-sheets for combined photothermal and chemotherapy of cancer. *Advanced materials*. 2014;26(21):3433-40.
35. Cheng L, Liu J, Gu X, Gong H, Shi X, Liu T, et al. PEGylated WS₂ nanosheets as a multifunctional theranostic agent for in vivo dual-modal CT/photoacoustic imaging guided photothermal therapy. *Advanced materials*. 2014;26(12):1886-93.
36. Chen Z, Zhang L, Sun Y, Hu J, Wang D. 980-nm Laser-Driven Photovoltaic Cells Based on Rare-Earth Up-Converting Phosphors for Biomedical Applications. *Advanced Functional Materials*. 2009;19(23):3815-20.
37. Tian Q, Jiang F, Zou R, Liu Q, Chen Z, Zhu M, et al. Hydrophilic Cu₉S₅ nanocrystals: a photothermal agent with a 25.7% heat conversion efficiency for photothermal ablation of cancer cells in vivo. *ACS nano*. 2011;5(12):9761-71.
38. Gonda K, Watanabe TM, Ohuchi N, Higuchi H. In vivo nano-imaging of membrane dynamics in metastatic tumor cells using quantum dots. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2010;285(4):2750-7.
39. Yang J, Dave SR, Gao X. Quantum dot nanobarcodes: epitaxial assembly of nanoparticle- polymer complexes in homogeneous solution. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2008;130(15):5286-92.
40. Pillai PP, Reisewitz S, Schroeder H, Niemeyer CM. Quantum-Dot-Encoded Silica Nanospheres for Nucleic Acid Hybridization. *Small*. 2010;6(19):2130-4.
41. Ma Q, Su X. Near-infrared quantum dots: synthesis, functionalization and analytical applications. *Analyst*. 2010;135(8):1867-77.
42. Chan WC, Nie S. Quantum dot bioconjugates for ultrasensitive nonisotopic detection. *Science*. 1998;281(5385):2016-8.

43. Kim HM, Lee H, Hong KS, Cho MY, Sung M-H, Poo H, et al. Synthesis and high performance of magnetofluorescent polyelectrolyte nanocomposites as MR/near-infrared multimodal cellular imaging nanoprobe. *ACS nano*. 2011;5(10):8230-40.
44. Li J, Wang H, Wei W, Meng L. Advanced MoS₂ and graphene heterostructures as high-performance anode for sodium-ion batteries. *Nanotechnology*. 2018.
45. Tanisaka H, Kizaka-Kondoh S, Makino A, Tanaka S, Hiraoka M, Kimura S. Near-infrared fluorescent labeled peptosome for application to cancer imaging. *Bioconjugate chemistry*. 2007;19(1):109-17.
46. Cao W, Ng KK, Corbin I, Zhang Z, Ding L, Chen J, et al. Synthesis and evaluation of a stable bacteriochlorophyll-analog and its incorporation into high-density lipoprotein nanoparticles for tumor imaging. *Bioconjugate chemistry*. 2009;20(11):2023-31.
47. Yang Z, Leon J, Martin M, Harder JW, Zhang R, Liang D, et al. Pharmacokinetics and biodistribution of near-infrared fluorescence polymeric nanoparticles. *Nanotechnology*. 2009;20(16):165101.